

Thyroid Hormone Receptor Gene Variants: Genetic Perspective on Hypothyroidism

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ABSTRACT

Hypothyroidism is one of the most common endocrine disorders worldwide, arising from diverse etiologies including primary thyroid gland failure, pituitary dysfunction, and hypothalamic disease, although levothyroxine remains the standard treatment, many patients continue to report persistent symptoms despite biochemical normalization, suggesting a role for receptor-level variability and the concept of tissue hypothyroidism. Thyroid hormone receptors (THR), encoded by THRA on chromosome 17 and THRB on chromosome 3, are nuclear transcription factors that mediate genomic and non-genomic actions of triiodothyronine. Review: Isoform-specific roles include TR α in cardiac, skeletal, and bone physiology, and TR β in hepatic metabolism and hypothalamic–pituitary regulation. Mutations in these receptors underlie resistance to thyroid hormone, with RTH β accounting for the majority of cases, while RTH α remains rare but clinically relevant. Beyond rare syndromes, single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) within THRA and THRB have been associated with variability in hypothyroidism risk, obesity, dyslipidemia, hypertension, asthma, reproductive dysfunction, and levothyroxine dose requirements. Functional studies further support the impact of receptor variants on transcriptional activity and hormone sensitivity.

Conclusion: the polygenic nature of thyroid dysfunction and emphasizes the potential of receptor polymorphism research to advance precision endocrinology, paving the way for genotype-guided therapy and receptor-targeted interventions.

Keywords: Thyroid hormone receptors, THRA, THRB, Polymorphism, Resistance to thyroid hormone.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Global Burden and Etiology of Hypothyroidism

Hypothyroidism describes one of the most widespread endocrine disorders worldwide, characterized by insufficient production or impaired action of the thyroid hormones triiodothyronine (T3) and thyroxine (T4). Depending on the level of

dysfunction within the hypothalamic–pituitary–thyroid (HPT) axis, its etiology can be broadly classified into primary, secondary, or tertiary forms (Table 1). Primary hypothyroidism results from intrinsic thyroid gland failure, secondary hypothyroidism arises from inadequate secretion of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) by the pituitary, and tertiary hypothyroidism reflects impaired thyrotropin-releasing hormone (TRH) secretion by the hypothalamus.

Table 1. Etiological classification of hypothyroidism

Primary Causes (Thyroid origin)	Secondary Causes (Pituitary origin)	Tertiary Causes (Hypothalamic origin)
Autoimmune thyroiditis (Hashimoto's)	Pituitary adenomas	Hypothalamic tumors
Iodine deficiency	Pituitary surgery	Hypothalamic irradiation

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Thyroidectomy	Suprasellar tumors	Trauma / infiltrative disease
Radioactive iodine therapy	Pituitary radiotherapy	Congenital TRH deficiency
External neck radiotherapy		
Antithyroid drugs, lithium, amiodarone		
Thyroid agenesis or dysgenesis		

Thyroid hormones play critical roles in skeletal growth, neurodevelopment, cardiovascular regulation, gastrointestinal motility, and systemic energy balance. Their synthesis and release are tightly regulated by the HPT axis through a negative feedback mechanism, in which circulating T3 and T4 inhibit pituitary TSH and hypothalamic TRH secretion¹.

1.2 Clinical Relevance and Genetic Perspectives

From a clinical perspective, thyroxine (T4) serves largely as a prohormone, while triiodothyronine (T3) is the biologically active form derived from both thyroidal secretion and peripheral deiodination. A deficiency of T3 underlies the classic manifestations of hypothyroidism. Epidemiological studies estimate the prevalence of overt hypothyroidism at 0.5–1.9% in women and <1% in men, while subclinical hypothyroidism is more common, affecting 3–13.6% of women and 0.7–5.7% of men². Overall, pooled data suggest prevalence rates of 3.9% for overt and 9.4% for subclinical hypothyroidism, with women disproportionately affected (11.4% vs. 6.2% in men³). Hospital-based studies have even reported prevalence as high as 43%, particularly among women⁴.

Despite effective biochemical control with levothyroxine replacement, a subset of patients continues to report persistent symptoms such as fatigue, weight gain, and cognitive dysfunction. This discrepancy has given rise to the concept of **cellular hypothyroidism**, wherein intracellular thyroid hormone action remains impaired despite normal serum hormone concentrations. At the molecular level, the biological actions of thyroid hormones are mediated by thyroid hormone receptors (THR_s), members of the nuclear receptor superfamily, which regulate gene expression through genomic and non-genomic mechanisms, thereby influencing protein

synthesis, mitochondrial activity, cell proliferation, and systemic metabolic homeostasis⁵.

Growing evidence depicts the role of thyroid hormone receptor gene polymorphisms in modulating receptor function, tissue sensitivity, and clinical phenotype. Variants may alter ligand binding affinity, transcriptional activity, or receptor stability, thereby contributing to interindividual variability in disease susceptibility and therapeutic outcomes. For instance, functional studies of the THR_B K146Q variant demonstrate impaired receptor stimulation and disruption of negative feedback regulation within the HPT axis⁶. Similarly, single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in related signaling components—such as the TSHR rs2268458 variant—have been associated with a threefold higher risk of hypothyroidism in Indian cohorts⁷ and confirmed across other populations⁸.

Large-scale genome-wide association studies (GWAS) further support the polygenic architecture of thyroid function, having identified hundreds of loci associated with TSH and free T4 levels⁹. Clinically, hypothyroidism manifests with a wide range of nonspecific symptoms—including cold intolerance, dermatological changes, constipation, and neurocognitive impairment—often diminishing quality of life. Given the high prevalence, persistent symptoms despite standard therapy, and growing recognition of receptor-mediated variability, the study of thyroid hormone receptor gene polymorphisms is both timely and essential. Such research holds the potential to advance precision endocrinology, paving the way for genotype-guided therapeutic strategies and receptor-targeted interventions.

2. Thyroid Hormone Receptor Signaling Pathway

Thyroid hormone receptors are ligand-activated transcription factors that belong to the nuclear receptor superfamily. They mediate the genomic

actions of triiodothyronine (T3), the active thyroid hormone, by binding to specific DNA sequences termed thyroid hormone response elements (TREs). In the unliganded state, TRs form heterodimers with retinoid X receptors (RXRs) and associate with nuclear co-repressors, resulting in chromatin condensation and transcriptional repression (Fig. 1). Upon T3 binding, co-repressors are released, co-activators are recruited, and transcription of target genes is initiated¹⁰.

Through this mechanism, thyroid hormones regulate diverse processes including oxygen consumption, basal metabolic rate, lipid and carbohydrate metabolism, skeletal growth, neurodevelopment, and negative feedback on hypothalamic TRH and pituitary TSH secretion¹¹.

Thyroid Hormone Receptor Pathway: Genomic Mechanism

Figure 1. Genomic mechanism of thyroid hormone receptor signaling, showing T3-mediated transcriptional activation and resulting physiological effects

3. DISCUSSION

Thyroid Hormone Receptor Gene Polymorphisms and Disease Associations

3.1 Rare Mutations and Resistance to Thyroid Hormone

Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) within THR genes can influence receptor binding affinity,

stability, or transcriptional activity, thereby altering tissue sensitivity to thyroid hormones. Variants in **THRB** have been implicated in **resistance to thyroid hormone (RTH)**, a rare condition characterized by elevated circulating thyroid hormones with inappropriately normal or raised TSH¹². Recent mechanistic studies demonstrated that the **THRB K146Q** variant disrupts receptor sumoylation, resulting in defective negative feedback at the hypothalamic–pituitary level and impaired regulation of thyroid hormone synthesis¹³.

3.2 Common Polymorphisms and Clinical Relevance

Beyond rare syndromes, common polymorphisms may contribute to variability in hypothyroidism susceptibility and therapeutic response. **Genome-wide association studies (GWAS)** have identified multiple loci, including **THRB**, **THRA**, and **TSHR**, that significantly influence serum TSH and free T4 concentrations¹⁴. Notably, the **TSHR rs2268458** variant was associated with a threefold higher risk of hypothyroidism in Indian cohorts, showing ethnic variability in genetic predisposition¹⁵. Parallel findings in European populations reinforce the broader contribution of receptor and pathway polymorphisms to thyroid dysfunction¹⁶.

Furthermore, polymorphisms in related genes—such as **deiodinase type 2 (DIO2 Thr92Ala)**—have been linked to persistent hypothyroid symptoms despite adequate levothyroxine therapy, supporting the concept of tissue-level hypothyroidism and the need for genotype-guided therapy¹⁷.

4. Complications of Hypothyroidism

4.1 Metabolic and Cardiovascular Complications

Hypothyroidism is associated with a broad spectrum of systemic complications, many of which significantly contribute to morbidity. Among these, metabolic syndrome has been consistently linked with thyroid dysfunction. Metabolic syndrome is defined by the presence of central obesity, hypertension, dyslipidemia, hyperglycemia, and proinflammatory or prothrombotic states, all of which increase cardiovascular risk¹⁸. Several Indian studies report hypothyroidism as the most frequent thyroid abnormality in patients with metabolic syndrome,

underscoring its regional relevance¹⁹. Thyroid hormones directly regulate lipid and glucose metabolism, vascular tone, and cardiac activity; therefore, their deficiency predisposes to cardiovascular disease²⁰.

Hypothyroidism is a recognized risk factor for atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD). Mechanistically, thyroid hormone deficiency elevates low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol and apolipoprotein B, both strongly atherogenic particles²¹. Clinical and experimental evidence confirms that overt hypothyroidism is consistently associated with increased concentrations of total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, and apolipoprotein B²². Hyperlipidemia is observed in over 90% of untreated hypothyroid patients, often accompanied by elevations in lipoprotein(a) and triglycerides²³.

4.2 Reproductive and Hormonal Complications

Reproductive health is also adversely impacted. Hypothyroidism prevalence in women of reproductive age ranges between 2% and 4%, with significant effects on fertility²⁴. Mechanisms include anovulation, luteal phase defects, altered gonadotropin secretion, and hyperprolactinemia²⁵. The presence of TSH receptors and thyroid hormone receptors in ovarian tissue and oocytes suggests direct ovarian involvement²⁶. Additionally, hypothyroidism alters estrogen and androgen metabolism by reducing sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG) concentrations, thereby disrupting hormonal balance²⁷. Menstrual irregularities are common, with oligomenorrhea reported in 25–60% of hypothyroid women compared with ~10% of euthyroid women²⁸. Moreover, hypothyroidism is linked to increased rates of infertility, miscarriage, and adverse pregnancy outcomes.

5. Thyroid Hormone Receptor Polymorphisms in Metabolic and Reproductive Dysfunction

Beyond systemic complications, **thyroid hormone receptor (THR) polymorphisms** contribute to disease variability. **THRA gene polymorphisms**, particularly rs1568400 and rs12939700, have been associated with obesity and hypertriglyceridemia²⁹. Thyroid hormones are fundamental regulators of basal metabolic rate, thermogenesis, lipid oxidation,

and glucose homeostasis. Even mild hypothyroidism or subclinical thyroid dysfunction has been correlated with increased body mass index (BMI) and central obesity³⁰. Leptin, secreted by adipocytes, modulates TRH secretion and deiodinase activity, providing a mechanistic link between thyroid dysfunction and obesity³¹.

Evidence suggests THRA dysfunction alters cardiac activity, bone metabolism, and thermogenesis in brown adipose tissue³². Knockout models demonstrate a ~20% reduction in heart rate and impaired thermogenesis when THRA is inactivated³³. Importantly, the **THRA isoforms (highlighted TR α 1 and TR α 2)** act antagonistically: TR α 1 mediates T3 action, while TR α 2 lacks the ligand-binding domain and negatively modulates TR α 1 signaling. Imbalances in isoform expression may contribute to altered tissue sensitivity.

Clinical studies have also polymorphisms such as **THRA rs939348**, which is linked to increased levothyroxine dose requirements and central obesity³⁴. This suggests a role for THR variants in metabolic syndrome, obesity, and differential treatment response. Furthermore, despite biochemically adequate replacement, many hypothyroid patients remain symptomatic, supporting the concept of **tissue hypothyroidism** and receptor-mediated resistance³⁵.

6. Genomic Location and Functional Domains of Thyroid Hormone Receptors

The **THRA** gene is located on chromosome 17, while the **THRB** gene resides on chromosome 3. Both encode members of the nuclear receptor superfamily that act as ligand-dependent transcription factors regulating gene expression. By modulating cell proliferation, differentiation, apoptosis, and survival, thyroid hormone receptors (TRs) play central roles in growth, development, reproduction, metabolic regulation, and homeostasis. Importantly, genetic alterations in TRs have been linked to autoimmune disease, coronary heart disease, and several malignancies, including breast, liver, pituitary, and renal cancers.³⁶

7. Isoform-Specific Expression and Physiological Roles

Thyroid hormone receptors (TRs) exhibit considerable isoform diversity, which directly influences their physiological functions across different organ systems. TR α 1 and TR α 2 are the predominant isoforms in bone, cardiac and skeletal muscle, the gastrointestinal tract, and the central nervous system, where they play pivotal roles in skeletal development, cardiac contractility, neural differentiation, and synaptic plasticity. TR α 1 acts as a functional receptor mediating triiodothyronine (T3) action, whereas TR α 2, despite sharing structural homology, lacks ligand-binding capacity and may act as a dominant-negative regulator. Conversely, TR β 1 and TR β 2 isoforms are enriched in metabolically active tissues such as the liver and kidney, as well as in neuroendocrine regions like the hypothalamus and pituitary. TR β 1 is essential for lipid and glucose metabolism, whereas TR β 2 is particularly important in feedback regulation of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) at the hypothalamic–pituitary level and in auditory and visual system development. This isoform-specific distribution highlights how receptor balance dictates the context-dependent and sometimes contrasting biological effects of thyroid hormones, underscoring their role in maintaining systemic metabolic and developmental homeostasis³⁷.

8. Resistance to Thyroid Hormone (RTH): Clinical Spectrum

Resistance to thyroid hormone (RTH) encompasses a heterogeneous group of disorders caused by mutations in TR genes, resulting in impaired target tissue responsiveness to T3. The most common form, RTH β , accounts for nearly 85% of cases and is typically associated with mutations in the THRB gene. Patients often exhibit a biochemical profile of elevated or normal serum T3 and T4 levels with inappropriately normal TSH, reflecting impaired negative feedback at the hypothalamic–pituitary axis. Clinically, RTH β presents with a paradoxical combination of thyrotoxic features—such as tachycardia, hyperactivity, and weight loss—alongside hypothyroid manifestations like fatigue,

learning difficulties, and impaired growth. By contrast, RTH α , caused by THRA mutations, is far less common and manifests primarily with features mimicking hypothyroidism, including constipation, growth retardation, bradycardia, and neurocognitive deficits, despite thyroid hormone levels often falling within reference ranges. A key diagnostic clue is a disproportionately low free T4/free T3 ratio with normal TSH³⁸. The clinical variability, ranging from asymptomatic carriers to individuals with severe phenotypes, makes diagnosis challenging, necessitating molecular genetic analysis for definitive identification and guiding therapeutic strategies.

9. Thyroid Hormone Transport Proteins and Diagnostic Clues

Thyroid hormone bioavailability and tissue distribution are tightly regulated by transport proteins in circulation. Approximately 75% of T4 is bound to thyroxine-binding globulin (TBG), the major carrier ensuring sustained hormone availability. Around 20% is bound to transthyretin (TTR), which facilitates transport across the blood–brain barrier, while about 5% associates with human serum albumin (HSA), acting as a reservoir for rapid mobilization. Less than 0.1% of thyroid hormones circulate as free fractions (fT3 and fT4), which are biologically active and readily available for receptor binding³⁹. Disturbances in this transport equilibrium can provide diagnostic insights: a pattern of high free T3 and T4 with normal TSH is suggestive of RTH β , whereas a reduced free T4/free T3 ratio with normal TSH strongly favors RTH α . Understanding these transport dynamics not only refines biochemical interpretation but also aids in differentiating true hormone resistance from other thyroid function test anomalies.

A summary of published studies examining **THR polymorphisms and their disease associations** is provided in **Table 2**.

Table 2 Studies done on THR SNP's and diseases associated with them:

Sl. No	Study conducted year	Receptor with rs numbers	Disease associated	Authors
1	2003	THR β rs13081063	Plasma TSH, no association found	Peeters et al
2	2008	THR α rs12939700	No association found with TSH levels	Sorensen et al
3	2008	THR β rs13063628	Associated with increased TSH level	Sorenson et al
4	2008	THR β rs1505287	Strongest association with TSH level	Lopez et al
5	2010	THR β rs9833191, rs4858608, rs3951794, rs2196427	Aggressive periodontitis	Carvalho et al
6	2010	THR β rs9310736	Two RBC traits, MCV & MCH	Kamatani et al
7	2011	THR α rs939348	Systolic BP and risk of hypertension	Goumidi et al
8	2011	THR α rs939348, rs1568400, rs3744805	Osteoarthritis (no association)	Meulenbelt et al
9	2012	THR α rs868150	Bronchodilator response in asthma	Duan et al
10	2012	THR β rs892940	Bronchodilator response in asthma	Duan et al
11	2013	THR α rs1568400	Obesity and dyslipidemia	Stephen WS et al
12	2013	THR α rs1568400	Obesity	Fernandez-Real et al
13	2014	THR α rs939348	Obesity	Sayer I et al
14	2018	THR α rs939348	Atherogenic dyslipidemia	Satwika Sinha et al
15	2021	THR α rs1568400	Overweight/obesity risk (adolescents; GRS component)	Seral-Cortés M et al
16	2021	THR α rs939348	Hyperthyroidism in women of child-bearing age	Wibowo A et al
17	2024	THR β truncated variants	Functional impact on THR β signaling (cell-based)	Rehman G et al
18	2025	THR β (missense SNP variants)	Functional effects in disease (in silico + cell assays)	Rehman G et al
19	2025	THR β rs1505287; rs4858608	Hypothyroidism risk (rs1505287 \uparrow), protective (rs4858608)	Kaur M et al

CONCLUSION

Single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) represent the most popular form of genetic variation in individuals, and their study has greatly advanced our understanding of how inherited factors influence phenotypic diversity and complex disease risk. In the context of thyroid activity, mutations and polymorphisms in its hormone receptor (THR) genes are increasingly recognized as important modulators of hormone sensitivity and clinical phenotype. **Resistance to thyroid hormone beta (RTH β)** typically manifests with normal or elevated

circulating its hormone concentrations and goitre, reflecting the critical role of **THR β** in destructive feedback regulation of the hypothalamic–pituitary–thyroid axis. By contrast, **RTH α** presents with near-normal thyroid hormone and TSH values, but clinical features of hypothyroidism such as growth delay and constipation. These findings emphasize that mutations in THR genes may be more prevalent than previously assumed, and genetic screening should be considered in patients with persistent hypothyroid symptoms but inconclusive laboratory results.

The clinical impact of thyroid dysfunction extends beyond hormone imbalance, notably influencing **fertility, menstrual health, and pregnancy outcomes**. While levothyroxine remains the mainstay of therapy, its benefit in individuals with subclinical hypothyroidism and mildly elevated TSH (2.5–4.0 mIU/L) remains debated, especially given the risk of overtreatment. Moreover, the concept of **tissue (cellular) hypothyroidism** has emerged to explain persistent symptoms in patients with biochemically adequate replacement, suggesting that receptor-level mechanisms are central to disease expression.

At the molecular level, THR_s regulate thyroid hormone action across genomic and non-genomic pathways, controlling cell proliferation, oxygen utilization, protein synthesis, and metabolic homeostasis. Advances in structural biology and ligand–receptor interaction studies hold promise for the development of **novel receptor-targeted therapies**. Notably, **THR_B-selective agonists** are under investigation as potential antidiabetic and anti-obesity agents due to their effects on lipid metabolism and adipose tissue reduction, though tissue specificity and safety remain to be fully defined. In summary, THR gene polymorphisms and receptor biology provide crucial insights into the heterogeneity of hypothyroidism. Future research integrating **genomics, functional assays, and clinical trials** is essential to translate these discoveries into **precision endocrinology**, offering genotype-guided management and improved therapeutic outcomes for patients with hypothyroidism.

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